

Synthesis and characterization of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5RT}$ molecular sieve at room temperature

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Abstract : Aluminophosphate molecular sieve $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5RT}$ ($\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$, prepared at room temperature) have been synthesized using hexamethylenimine template at room temperature for the first time. Gel composition $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 : \text{P}_2\text{O}_5 : 1.16\text{HEM} : 45\text{H}_2\text{O}$ aging for 12 h at room temperature, and in 24 h, 473 K are the standard reaction conditions for synthesis of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$. Studies on above gel composition at room temperature shows the presence of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ crystals. Both the aluminophosphates have been characterized by elemental analysis, XRD, SEM, FT-IR, TG/DTA, and ^{13}C , ^{27}Al and ^{31}P MASNMR techniques. XRD analysis of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5RT}$ shows that the presence of low intensity pseudoboehmite sample. SEM shows the morphology nanosized crystals along with platelets. TG/DTA analysis reveals the presence of maximum five stages elimination of templates. Carbon and nitrogen analysis shows that the presence of four template molecules per unit cell. ^{13}C MASNMR analysis shows the interaction of template with structure of the framework. ^{27}Al MASNMR shows the presence of small amount of octahedral co-ordination besides the rest are in tetrahedral co-ordination. ^{31}P MASNMR shows the presence of two environmentally different tetrahedrally co-ordinated phosphorous atoms.

Keywords : Molecular sieve, aluminophosphate.

A new generation of molecular sieves, aluminophosphates (AlPO_4s) were reported by Wilson *et al.* having framework compositions comprising $[\text{AlO}_2]^-$ and $[\text{PO}_2]^+$ tetrahedra¹⁻³. Aluminophosphate molecular sieves are the first reported novel class of crystalline microporous oxide framework structures synthesized without silica^{1,4}. These molecular sieves are similar to zeolites in some properties and it has been claimed that they may be used as adsorbents, catalysts and catalyst supports. The new AlPO_4 family currently includes about twenty two three dimensional framework structures of which at least sixteen are microporous and six are two dimensional layer type materials. Most of these three dimensional structures are novel, e.g. $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$, -31, -41 and -22. Some of the aluminophosphates are structurally similar to zeolites, e.g. $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-17}$ (erionite) and SAPO-35 (levynite). The neutral aluminophosphate frameworks with no extra framework cations are moderately hydrophilic. Their framework composition with an Al/P ratio of 1 has a wide structural diversity.

Aluminophosphates are synthesized hydrothermally in the temperature range 373–531 K from a reaction mixture containing sources of aluminium, phosphorous and an organic amine or a quaternary ammonium salt⁵ which gets entrapped or clathrated within the crystalline products. Since the aluminophosphate framework is electrically neutral, the template is not needed as a charge balancing agent; there-

fore, its incorporation into the structure is a function of its electronic nature, size and shape relative to the channel volume to be filled. The entrapped organic species are removed by thermal decomposition. Moreover, these novel structures exhibit thermal stability. Most of these remain crystalline after calcination around 400–600 °C, which is necessary for the removal of the organic template and make the intracrystalline void volume free for the adsorption and catalysis. A single template can give rise to multiple AlPO_4 structures and a variety of structures can be synthesized from a single template. $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ is synthesized using a large variety of organic templates. On the contrary $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-16}$ has been synthesized with only one template, namely, quinuclidine¹. In the present work the synthesis of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ at room temperature using hexamethyleneimine template is reported. The material have been characterized by conventional techniques like XRD, SEM FT-IR, TG/DTA, and ^{13}C , ^{27}Al and ^{31}P MASNMR. The $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ sample synthesized at higher temperature was taken for comparison purpose.

Results and discussion

The elemental composition of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ prepared by both the methods are similar to the reported values^{1,2}. Calcined $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ on saturation with hexamethyleneimine sorbed 0.59 molecule per unit cell. The as-synthesized

form of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$, synthesized using hexamethyleneimine at higher temperature contained two template per unit cell. However, $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ synthesized using the same template in room temperature contain four templates ($C = 19.038$ and $N = 3.537\%$) per unit cell. This is sterically possible if one template is packed tight over the other two along the c -direction of the unit cell. The template is less tightly packed in the case of the $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ synthesized at higher temperature, as two template molecules are present per unit cell in the sample. The elemental composition of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ synthesized at both temperatures consists of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 : 0.99\text{P}_2\text{O}_5$.

Table 1. TG/DTA data of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ molecular sieves synthesized using hexamethyleneimine

Sample	Weight loss, % (temp °C)				
	I stage (Endo)	II stage (Endo)	III stage (Exo)	IV stage (Exo)	V stage (Exo)
$\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$	6.4 (25–211)	–	5 (211–404)	6.5 (404–615)	–
$\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5RT}$	4.7 (25–113)	7.48 (113–257)	5.68 (257–326)	14.71 (326–442)	5.28 (442–816)

Fig. 1 X-Ray diffraction patterns of (a) catapal B, (b) $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5RT}$ and (c) $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$

The X-ray diffraction patterns of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ synthesized at both the temperatures are presented in Fig. 1. The X-ray diffraction patterns of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ synthesized at room temperature is containing weak pseudo-boehmite peaks the other sample is similar to $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ published patterns^{5,6,8}. The thermal stability of both the samples are same.

The SEM photographs show that the morphology and particle size (Fig. 2) depend on method. $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ synthe-

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 2. Scanning electron microscopic photographs of (a) catapal B, (b) $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ and (c) $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$

sized at higher temperature was having cauliflower shape with size $14\ \mu\text{m}$. However, the room temperature synthesized sample containing nanocrystals along with platelets.

The TG/DTA plots are presented in Fig. 3(a,b). The weight loss of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ occurs in three to five stages (Table 1). The first stage endothermic loss at $100\ ^\circ\text{C}$ is due to loss of physisorbed water and template. In the case of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ physisorbed material loss occur in a single step. However, $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5RT}$ loses the same in two different stages at 93 and $133\ ^\circ\text{C}$ due to its very small pore openings of amorphous materials. The oxidative decomposition of hexamethyleneimine occurs in three stages in $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5RT}$ against two stages in $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$.

Based on carbon and nitrogen analysis the number of template molecules per unit cell was calculated and percentage of weight loss was also deduced. These values are

Fig. 3. TGA (1) and DTA (2) of (b) $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5RT}$ and (c) $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$. compared with TG-DTA weight loss. $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ is expected to give 13.52% weight loss, but it actually gave 17.9% loss. In the same way $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5RT}$ gave 37.85%, while it was expected to give 22.575%. These extra loss in TG/DTA analysis are due to the loss of physisorbed water and template.

FT-IR spectra recorded in the framework region of the aluminophosphates, $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ and $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5RT}$ are presented in Fig. 4. Both are looking similar. They give bands at 1074(vs), 968(wsh), 735(w), 610(vw), 480(m) were assigned⁷ to T-O-T (where T = Al or P) asymmetric, symmetric stretching, double ring, bending and pore opening vibrations. The peak positions in $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ shifted to higher values due to shrink in pore size compared $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5RT}$.

The ^{13}C NMR spectrum of pure liquid hexamethylenimine (Fig. 5) consists of three sharp lines at $\delta = 27.60$ and 49.74 ppm due to the three non equivalent pairs of c-atoms viz. C_3/C_4 , C_2/C_5 , C_1/C_6 respectively. In the case of hexamethylenimine occluded in $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5RT}$ and $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$, the two lines (Fig. 5) in the high field region are not re-

Fig. 4. FT-IR spectra of (a) catapal B, (b) $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5RT}$ and (c) $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ in the framework region

Fig. 5. ^{13}C NMR spectra of (a) liquid hexamethylenimine, (b) $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5RT}$ and (c) $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$

Fig 6 ^{27}Al (a) and ^{31}P (b) MASNMR of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5RT}$

solved resulting in a broad single double intense line at ~ 39.5 ppm and a single low intensity line 60.00 ppm due to restriction in the movement of the template inside the molecular sieves. The channel dimension of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ (cross section $7.3 \text{ \AA}$ and c-repeat distance $8.4 \text{ \AA}$) can easily accommodate the hexamethylenimine molecule. ^{27}Al MASNMR of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5RT}$ shows (Fig 6) three peaks at 42 , 9 and -11 ppm for tetrahedrally co-ordinated aluminium, unreacted octahedrally co-ordinated alumina and octahedrally co-ordinated aluminium with water. ^{31}P MASNMR shows two prominent peaks at -18 and -28 ppm for environmentally different tetrahedrally co-ordinated phosphorus atoms.

Although XRD, SEM, TG/DTA are different for $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ from $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5RT}$, but similar in FT-IR and MASNMR properties. Earlier reports reveal that due to the small crystals less than 8 nm , the FT-IR active molecular sieves are not positive to XRD⁹. Here the same results observed from SEM photograph.

The solvent employed in the synthesis of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5RT}$ is essentially water. An important aspect of the synthesis of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5RT}$ is the use of hexamethylenimine as the templating agent. Hexamethylenimine owing to its bigger size (heterocyclic ring) has little chance to act as a template during the synthesis of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$. In our system we believe that hexamethylenimine and the solvent interact during the reaction leading to the formation of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5RT}$ and its suc-

cessful synthesis suggests that other suitable templating agents for different $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-n}$ structures in room temperature may be found.

Conclusion

In summary, the synthesis of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5RT}$ will contribute substantially to our understanding of the nature and chemistry of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-n}$ and other related materials. Owing to the greater diversity of room temperature synthesis, there is a considerable potential for the synthesis of a variety of novel molecular sieves by the use of this technique.

Experimental

The typical procedure for the synthesis of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5RT}$ is as follows: 7.16 g of catapal B (74.2% Al_2O_3 , Vista Chemicals, USA) was mixed with 20 ml of distilled water and stirred well. 11.5 g of orthophosphoric acid (85% , s.d. fine, India) was added dropwise to the mixture and stirred well. A white thick paste was formed, which was aged overnight. 5.82 g of hexamethylenimine (98% , Aldrich, USA) along with 20 ml of distilled water was mixed well with the paste and the resulting gel ($\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{P}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot 1.6\text{HEM} \cdot 4.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) was centrifuged and washed well with distilled water. The resulting solid was dried at 110°C and subjected to physicochemical characterization. A portion of the same was calcined at 550°C for 8 h . The temperature was raised at the rate of $1.5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ from room temperature. A portion of the gel was charged into a teflon lined autoclave and crystallized for 24 h at 200°C ($\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$)⁶. The product is cooled, washed several times with distilled water and dried at 110°C and subjected to physicochemical characterization.

The samples synthesized during the course of work were analyzed by X-ray powder diffraction (Rigaku, Model D/MAX III VC, Japan, Ni filtered $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$ radiation, $\lambda = 1.5404 \text{ \AA}$, graphite crystal monochromator, computer controlled automated diffractometer). The morphologies of all the aluminophosphates synthesized were investigated using a scanning electron microscope (JEOL, JSM 5200). The framework region ($400\text{--}1300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) of the synthesized aluminophosphates were analyzed using a Nicolet 60SXB FT-IR instrument in the diffuse reflectance mode using a $1:300$ ratio of the sample to KBr mixture. Simultaneous TG/DTA analysis of the crystalline phases were performed on an automatic derivatograph (Setaram TG-DTA 92). ^{13}C MASNMR spectra were recorded in the solid state with a Bruker MSL 300 spectrometer operating at a field 7 Tesla and recorded at 75.57 MHz . The Hartman-Han match conditions were established using adamantane (typically a match condition of 50 KHz was employed). The chemical shifts were referred to with respect to the C-H peak of ad-

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amantane (38.7 ppm). A spinning speed of ~3 KHz was used. ²⁷Al and ³¹P MASNMR spectra were recorded in the solid state with a Bruker DRX 500 spectrometer operating at a field of 11.7 Tesla. ²⁷Al spectra were recorded at a frequency of 130.3 MHz, with a pulse length of 2 μs and a spinning speed of 3–5 KHz. ³¹P spectra were recorded at a frequency of 202.45 MHz with a pulse length of 1.5 μs and the recycle delay was 4 s. 1 M Al(NO₃)₃ and 1 M H₃PO₄ solutions (for aluminium and phosphorous) were used as standards.

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